

Ancillary Services Prioritization in Inverters with Virtual Synchronous Generator Functionalities

Eleni Tekki¹, Lenos Hadjidemetriou¹, Manuel Barragan-Villarejo², Francisco Jesus Matas-Diaz²,
Jose Maria Maza-Ortega², Antonio Gomez-Explosito², Marios M. Polycarpou¹.

¹KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence and Dept. of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus

²Dept. of Electrical Engineering, Universidad de Sevilla, Sevilla, Spain

Abstract—The massive integration of renewable energy reduces the overall inertia of the grid deteriorating the system stability. Virtual synchronous generator approaches have been recently introduced in the inverter controller to enable distributed resources to improve the power system stability through frequency support. At the same time, ancillary services can be provided by the inverters to compensate reactive power flow and loading asymmetries, improving in this way the efficiency and utilization of distribution grids. This work proposes a novel multi-functional inverter where the virtual synchronous generator mode for frequency support is combined with ancillary services provision capabilities for phase balancing and reactive power compensation. In this context, an algorithm is proposed to prioritize online the provision of each functionality in order to guarantee the overcurrent limits of the inverter under any operating conditions. The inverter performance is validated through simulations, indicating that it can be reliably used to improve the power system operation.

Index Terms—Ancillary services, inverter, phase balancing, reactive compensation, virtual synchronous generator.

I. INTRODUCTION

Future power systems will be dominated by the massive presence of renewable energy sources (RESs) deployed at all grid levels. This entails a transformation of the traditional generation where synchronous generators will be replaced by inverters, the key devices responsible for the grid integration of RES. Among other challenges, this transformation reduces the system inertia and thus, the frequency stability is threatened [1]. Therefore, in inverter-dominated power grids, it is crucial that the frequency and voltage control of the system is provided by both inverters and conventional generation plants [2]. In addition, the distribution grids are also facing several challenges. For example, reactive power loads are reducing the power factor while single-phase connected appliances are introducing intense asymmetric loading conditions. As a result, the energy losses are increased, and the grid utilization is restricted due to the reactive current flow and the unequal allocation of the loading conditions among the three phases [3]. Furthermore, non-linear loads (e.g., DC loads) are causing harmonic distortion which deteriorates the power quality of distribution grids. Thus, the nodal voltages are highly distorted [2] while transformers and lines are overheated.

Traditionally, shunt capacitors have been installed at the grid edge to compensate low power factor phenomena [4], while dedicated hardware devices for switching the phase connection of a consumer has been suggested to deal with the load asymmetries [5]. Furthermore, dedicated power electronics converters have been proposed to compensate for the undesired operating conditions in distribution grids. For example, a static var compensator can be used to provide power factor correction functionalities [6], while an active filter can compensate asymmetric or harmonic loading conditions [7]. However, the installation of such dedicated devices involves a high capital investment which restricts their wide deployment.

A more cost-effective solution involves the utilization of typical voltage source inverters used for the grid-integration of RES or energy storage systems (ESSs) not only to deliver the produced power into the grid but also to provide grid support functionalities and ancillary services (ASs). Such multi-functional inverters require an advanced control strategy, where the synchronization can be achieved either (a) by following the grid voltage conditions through a phase locked loop (PLL) approach [3], [8]-[10], or (b) by defining their own phase angle and frequency according to droop control approaches or virtual synchronous generator (VSG) characteristics [11]-[14]. In the first category with the PLL synchronized inverters, an enhanced voltage and frequency controller has been proposed under fault ride through operation [8], in which virtual inertia and frequency droop support functions are combined with an optimal voltage support scheme that takes into account the highly resistive characteristics of distribution grids. Furthermore, the provision of additional AS have been proposed for such PLL synchronized inverters, enabling: reactive power compensation for a unity power factor [9]; phase balancing services [3], [9], [10]; and active filtering services for compensating the harmonic distortion [10]. In the second category, where the inverter independently determines its phase angle, a grid-connected mode is ensured by utilizing only a current controller, while both grid-connected and stand-alone operation can be achieved when a grid voltage controller is employed as well. In this framework, the concept of virtual synchronous generator (VSG) has emerged [11]-[12], which can mimic the behavior of conventional generators by emulating inertia to provide frequency and voltage forming

The authors from University of Cyprus are supported in part by the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101075747 (TRANSIT), in part by the Republic of Cyprus through the Research and Innovation Foundation under Project CULTURE/ AWARD-YR/0322B/0003 (INVERGE), and in part by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739551 (KIOS CoE) and from the Republic of Cyprus through the Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy. The authors from Universidad de Sevilla are supported under Grant PID2021-124571OB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by "ERDF A way of making Europe". The e-mail of the corresponding author is: etekki01@ucy.ac.cy.

time active power injected by the inverter in p.u computed according to the positive sequence voltage (\mathbf{v}^+) and current (\mathbf{i}^+) (decomposed by the DN $\alpha\beta$) and, k_p^p and k_i^p are the proportional and integral gains of the active power PI controller, respectively. The proportional term of the active power loop represents the damping of the synchronous generator while the integral term emulates the inertia response according to [12].

The virtual electromotive force e of the VSG is calculated by the reactive power control loop, as given by (3),

$$e = e^* + k_p^q(Q^{+*} - \bar{Q}^+) + k_i^q \int (Q^{+*} - \bar{Q}^+) \quad (3)$$

where e^* is the reference electromotive force in p.u, Q^{+*} is the reactive power reference in p.u to allow reactive power compensation services, $\bar{Q}^+ = \mathbf{v}^+ \times \mathbf{i}^+$ is the real-time reactive power injected by the inverter calculated according to the positive sequence voltage and current (as estimated by the DN $\alpha\beta$), while k_p^q and k_i^q are the proportional and integral gains of the PI controller used in the reactive power control loop.

The virtual frequency ω_{VSG} , angle θ_{VSG} and electromotive force e , as generated by (1)-(3), are used to compute the positive sequence current reference vectors in the synchronous dq -frame, $\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{+*} = [i_d^{+*} \ i_q^{+*}]^T$, that will be fed as an input to the current control loop. The reference current signals are generated according to (4)-(5), following the virtual impedance concept [20], which is contributing to decouple the active and reactive power injection by the voltage source inverter as well.

$$i_d^{+*} = \frac{(Re - R_v v_d^+ - X_v v_q^+)}{R_v^2 + X_v^2} \quad (4)$$

$$i_q^{+*} = \frac{(-X_v e + X_v v_d^+ - R_v v_q^+)}{R_v^2 + X_v^2} \quad (5)$$

In (4)-(5), R_v and X_v are the virtual resistance and reactance, respectively, and v_d^+ and v_q^+ are the positive sequence voltage at the PCC, expressed in dq -frame, as estimated by the DN $\alpha\beta$. It is noted that the reference current vector \mathbf{i}_{dq}^{+*} is provided as an input to an advanced current controller, which has capabilities to regulate both positive and negative sequence current [3].

B. Ancillary Services Provision and Prioritization

Based on the angle θ_{VSG} generated by the VSG unit, the DN $\alpha\beta$ [19] is used to dynamically decompose the PCC voltage (\mathbf{v}), the inverter current (\mathbf{i}) and the load current (\mathbf{i}_L) into their positive (\mathbf{v}^+ , \mathbf{i}^+ , \mathbf{i}_L^+) and negative (\mathbf{v}^- , \mathbf{i}^- , \mathbf{i}_L^-) sequence components. Each positive or negative sequence voltage or current vector, denoted as \mathbf{x}^+ or \mathbf{x}^- , can be expressed in dq -frame, as given by (6)-(7).

$$\mathbf{x}^+ = \sqrt{3/2} \mathbf{x}_{dq}^+ = \sqrt{3/2} [x_d^+ \ x_q^+]^T \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{x}^- = \sqrt{3/2} \mathbf{x}_{dq}^- = \sqrt{3/2} [x_d^- \ x_q^-]^T \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_{dq}^+ = [x_d^+ \ x_q^+]^T$ and $\mathbf{x}_{dq}^- = [x_d^- \ x_q^-]^T$ can represent \mathbf{v}_{dq}^+ , \mathbf{i}_{dq}^+ , \mathbf{i}_{L-dq}^+ and \mathbf{v}_{dq}^- , \mathbf{i}_{dq}^- , \mathbf{i}_{L-dq}^- vectors, respectively, expressed in the corresponding positive or negative rotating dq -frames. Assuming that the negative sequence of the voltage at the PCC is neglected ($\mathbf{v}^- \approx 0$), then an advanced power system analysis is performed by the PQ calculation block to calculate

the following quantities that will enable the provision of AS for reactive power compensation and phase balancing services.

For the reactive power compensation, the reactive power consumed by the load should first be calculated, as given by,

$$Q_L = \mathbf{v}^+ \times \mathbf{i}_L = \mathbf{v}_\perp^+ \cdot \mathbf{i}_L = \mathbf{v}_\perp^+ \cdot \mathbf{i}_L^+ + \mathbf{v}_\perp^+ \cdot \mathbf{i}_L^- \quad (8)$$

where the first non-oscillating term corresponds to the positive sequence reactive power \bar{Q}_L^+ , with a mean value given by (9), the second term corresponds to an oscillating (double frequency) reactive power \tilde{Q}_L^- due to the asymmetric current absorption (\mathbf{i}_L^-), and $\mathbf{v}_\perp^+ = \sqrt{3/2} [v_q^+ \ -v_d^+]^T$ is defined as an orthogonal vector, leading the initial voltage vector \mathbf{v}^+ by 90° . For the reactive power compensation to achieve a unity power factor, the mean value of the positive sequence reactive power \bar{Q}_L^+ , calculated by (9), needs to be compensated.

$$\bar{Q}_L^+ = \mathbf{v}_\perp^+ \cdot \mathbf{i}_L^+ = (3/2)(v_q^+ i_{L-d}^+ - v_d^+ i_{L-q}^+) \quad (9)$$

Similarly, the active power of the load is expressed by (10),

$$P_L = \mathbf{v}^+ \cdot \mathbf{i}_L = \mathbf{v}^+ \cdot (\mathbf{i}_L^+ + \mathbf{i}_L^-) = \mathbf{v}^+ \cdot \mathbf{i}_L^+ + \mathbf{v}^+ \cdot \mathbf{i}_L^- \quad (10)$$

where the first non-oscillating term is the positive sequence active power \bar{P}_L^+ , and the second term is the oscillating active power \tilde{P}_L^- associated with the load negative sequence current. For phase balancing services, the negative sequence load current \mathbf{i}_L^- should be compensated by the inverter through a specific negative sequence apparent power S_L^- , that is directly associated to \mathbf{i}_L^- . \tilde{S}_L^- is an oscillating power due to the combination of the positive sequence voltage \mathbf{v}^+ and the negative sequence current \mathbf{i}_L^- , given by (11).

$$\tilde{S}_L^- = \tilde{P}_L^- + j\tilde{Q}_L^- = (\mathbf{v}^+ \cdot \mathbf{i}_L^-) + j(\mathbf{v}_\perp^+ \cdot \mathbf{i}_L^-) \quad (11)$$

Therefore, the total amplitude of the negative sequence apparent power that needs to be compensated is calculated by,

$$|\tilde{S}_L^-| = |\mathbf{v}^+| |\mathbf{i}_L^-| \quad (12)$$

where $|\mathbf{i}_L^-| = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}(i_{L-d}^{-2} + i_{L-q}^{-2})}$ and $|\mathbf{v}^+| = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}(v_d^{+2} + v_q^{+2})}$.

The load powers \bar{Q}_L^+ and $|\tilde{S}_L^-|$ calculated according to (9) and (12), respectively, represent the required AS provision (e.g., reactive power, negative sequence apparent power) to

Figure 2. Flowchart of the process of prioritisation of ASs.

achieve full compensation. This is feasible if there is enough inverter capacity. However, when the inverter current limits are violated, then the provision of AS should be restricted to prevent overloading while giving a priority order to each AS.

The flowchart of the proposed prioritization method is presented in Figure 2. First, the algorithm checks if the apparent power arising from the real-time positive sequence active power injection by the inverter, $P^+ = \mathbf{v}^+ \cdot \mathbf{i}^+$ (including RES production and virtual inertia response as well), and the provision of full compensation ASs (e.g., \bar{Q}_L^+ and $|\bar{S}_L^-|$), is within the inverter nominal limits (S_n), according to (13).

$$S_n \geq \sqrt{P^{+2} + \bar{Q}_L^{+2}} + |\bar{S}_L^-| \quad (13)$$

If (13) is true, then full compensation can be achieved and thus, the AS reference signals for positive sequence reactive power $Q^{+*} = \bar{Q}_L^+$ and the negative sequence current $\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{-*} = \mathbf{i}_{L-dq}^-$ are determined according to the loading conditions. However, if (13) is not valid, then there is not enough inverter capacity to achieve full compensation given the business-as-usual operation (P^+) of the inverter. Consequently, the AS reference signals should be reduced to ensure the inverter current limits considering a prioritization approach.

In the approach proposed in Figure 2, a higher priority is given to reactive power compensation over phase balancing. Thus, the algorithm checks (14) to evaluate if full reactive power compensation services can be provided given the business-as-usual operation of the inverter.

$$S_n \geq \sqrt{P^{+2} + \bar{Q}_L^{+2}} \quad (14)$$

If (14) is valid, then full reactive power compensation can be provided while the phase balancing service is restricted to achieve the maximum possible phase balancing services without violating the inverter limits, according to the following AS reference signals given by (15), (16).

$$Q^{+*} = \bar{Q}_L^+ \quad (15)$$

$$\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{-*} = \left(\frac{2}{3}\right) \frac{\left|S_n - \sqrt{P^{+2} + \bar{Q}_L^{+2}}\right|}{|\mathbf{v}_{dq}^+|} \angle \arctan\left(\frac{i_{L-dq}^-}{i_{L-d}^-}\right) \quad (16)$$

On the other hand, if (14) is not satisfied, then phase balancing services cannot be provided and additionally, reactive power compensation must be restricted to the maximum support that will not violate the inverter limits. In this case the AS references signals are given by (17)-(18).

$$Q^{+*} = \sqrt{S_n^2 - P^{+2}} \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{i}_{dq}^{-*} = 0 \quad (18)$$

It is noted that in all cases, a higher priority is always provided to the active power injection as required by both the RES generation and the virtual inertia response (under a frequency event). Thus, the business-as-usual operation of the VSG-based inverter is not affected by the AS provision.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

The performance of the proposed control scheme of the VSG inverter with AS provision capabilities is validated

through a simulation-based investigation. A 5kVA three-phase PV inverter connected to a LV power grid is simulated using MATLAB/Simulink, where the configuration and the proposed controller presented in Figure 1 are digitally integrated. Figure 3 demonstrates the simulation results regarding the power components injected by the inverter ($P^+, \bar{Q}^+, \bar{S}^-$) compared to the undesired power components consumed by the load (\bar{Q}_L^+, \bar{S}_L^-) that needs to be compensated, the total power components exchanged with the grid (\bar{Q}_G^+, \bar{S}_G^-), and the maximum available inverter capacity for reactive power compensation (\bar{Q}_{max}^+) and phase balancing provision (\bar{S}_{max}^-). It is noted that grid power components are estimated as $\bar{Q}_G^+ = \mathbf{v}_L^+ \cdot \mathbf{i}_G^+$, $\bar{S}_G^- = |\mathbf{v}^-| \cdot |\mathbf{i}_G^-|$, where \mathbf{i}_G^+ and \mathbf{i}_G^- are the positive and negative sequence components of the grid current (\mathbf{i}_G). When $\bar{Q}_G^+ = 0$, it is indicated that a unity power factor is achieved by the inverter ASs provision, while $\bar{S}_G^- = 0$ denotes a fully symmetrized loading interaction between the prosumer and the grid.

At the beginning of the simulation in Figure 3 ($t < 2$ s), the ASs support is deactivated, the grid frequency is set to 50 Hz, the inverter active power production is 2.2 kW, and the load connected at the same PCC is consuming active, reactive, and negative sequence power. Thus, when $t < 2$ s, the inverter injects only active power P^+ , based on the reference value of the VSG controller, to ensure maximum power production, while the grid reactive power (\bar{Q}_G^+) and unbalance (\bar{S}_G^-) are not eliminated. This can also be verified by the steady state current injection demonstrated in Figure 4(a), where the inverter current (\mathbf{i}) is purely symmetrical and the grid current (\mathbf{i}_G) is highly asymmetrical with a non-unity power factor.

At $t = 2$ s, the ASs algorithm is activated and therefore the inverter injects reactive (\bar{Q}^+) and negative sequence (\bar{S}^-) power to compensate the existing loading conditions. In this case, the inverter capacity is enough to provide full compensation, since

Figure 3. Simulation results demonstrating (from top to bottom): i) VSG frequency, ii) active power, iii) reactive power iv) negative apparent power.

Figure 4. Simulation results showing load (i_L), inverter (i), and grid (i_G) current when the ASs: (a) are deactivated, (b) provide full reactive compensation and phase balancing, (c) provide full reactive compensation and partial phase balancing, and (d) provide a partial reactive compensation.

the condition in (13) is valid. As a result, the inverter is able to provide reactive compensation equal to \tilde{Q}_L^+ and phase balancing services equal to \tilde{S}_L^- , achieving ideal power exchange conditions with a total elimination of the grid reactive power and negative sequence apparent power ($\tilde{Q}_G^+ = \tilde{S}_G^- = 0$). This is also indicated in Figure 4(b), where the inverter current (i) is asymmetrical and the grid current (i_G) purely symmetrical.

For $t \geq 4$ s, the active power reference is increased, representing an increased production by the RES, which reduces the inverter's capacities for ASs (\tilde{Q}_{max}^+ , \tilde{S}_{max}^-). Since the remaining capacity of the inverter is not sufficient to fully compensate for both reactive power and unbalances, and since a priority is given to reactive power compensation according to the AS provision algorithm, a reduced phase balancing service is provided. As a result, the negative sequence grid power exchange \tilde{S}_G^- is not fully eliminated in Figure 3, while the grid current is slightly asymmetrical in Figure 4(c).

At $6 \leq t \leq 11$ s, a frequency disturbance occurs, where the frequency is linearly reducing to 49.5 Hz with a rate of change of frequency ($RoCoF$) equal to 0.1 Hz/s. During the frequency disturbance, the active power is increased by 1.57 kW, according to the VSG inertia response. The increase of active power reduces the maximum capacity for ASs. In this case, the phase balancing service is totally eliminated, leading to significantly asymmetrical grid power exchange ($\tilde{S}_G^- = \tilde{S}_L^-$ in Figure 3) and intense asymmetric grid current condition as indicated by the i_G waveform in Figure 4(d). Furthermore, an additional reactive power compensation decrease is applied, as indicated by (17), to maintain the thermal limits of the inverter under the active power injection during the frequency event. In this case, \tilde{Q}_G^+ is not zero and thus, a unity power factor is not maintained between the prosumer and the grid.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work proposes a multi-functional RES inverter controller with a VSG approach to enhance the stability of inverter-dominated power systems, along with ASs provision

to compensate reactive power and asymmetric loading conditions in distribution grids. An online AS prioritization method is also developed to effectively coordinate the provision of AS while ensuring the inverter limits under any operating conditions. Hence, the developed inverter can beneficially affect modern power grids in terms of stability, power quality, efficiency and utilization of existing grid capacity.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Gu, R. Yan, and T. K. Saha, "Minimum synchronous inertia requirement of renewable power systems," *IEEE Trans. Power Systems*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 1533–1543, 2018.
- [2] A. Huda and R. Zivanovic, "Large-scale integration of distributed generation into distribution networks: Study objectives, review of models and computational tools," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 76, pp. 974–988, 09 2017.
- [3] L. Hadjidemetriou, L. Zacharia, and E. Kyriakides, "Flexible power control scheme for interconnected photovoltaics to benefit the power quality and network losses of the distribution grid," in *Proc. IEEE ECCE-Asia*, Kaohsiung, 2017, pp. 1–6.
- [4] B. R. Pereira, et al., "Optimal distributed generation and reactive power allocation in electrical distribution systems," *IEEE Trans. Sustainable Energy*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 975–984, July 2016.
- [5] S. Kadam and B. Bletterie, "Balancing the grid with single-phase PV installations," in *Proc. IEEE ISIE*, Edinburgh, 2017, pp. 63–69.
- [6] V. M. López-Martín, et al., "Power Quality Enhancement in Residential Smart Grids Through Power Factor Correction Stages," *IEEE Trans. Industrial Electronics*, vol. 65, no. 11, pp. 8553–8564, Nov. 2018.
- [7] M. M. Hashempour, et al., "A control architecture to coordinate distributed generators and active power filters coexisting in a microgrid," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 2325–2336, Sep. 2016.
- [8] A. Charalambous, et al., "A coordinated voltage-frequency support scheme for storage systems connected to distribution grids," *IEEE Trans. Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 7, pp. 8464–8475, July. 2021.
- [9] A. Charalambous, et al., "Flexible Provision of Ancillary Services by Grid-Tied Inverters," in *Proc. IEEE APEC*, pp. 1904–1911, 2022.
- [10] Z. Ali, et al., "Diversifying the role of distributed generation grid side converters for improving the power quality of distribution networks using advanced control techniques," *IEEE Trans. Industry Applications*, vol. 55, no. 4, pp. 4110–4123, Aug. 2019.
- [11] D. Terazono, J. Liu, Y. Miura, S. Sakabe, H. Bevrani, and T. Ise, "Grid frequency regulation support from back-to-back motor drive system with virtual-synchronous-generator-based coordinated control," *IEEE Trans. Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 2901–2913, Mar. 2021.
- [12] G. C. Kryonidis, et al., "A new perspective on the synchronverter model," *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 140, p. 108072, 2022.
- [13] Y. Han, et al., "Control strategies for islanded microgrid using enhanced hierarchical control structure with multiple current-loop damping schemes," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 1139–1153, 2017.
- [14] F. J. Matas-Diaz, et al., "Active harmonic filtering of islanded converter interfaced generation considering the thermal limits," in *Proc. IEEE SEST*, pp. 1–6, 2022.
- [15] L. Huang, et al., "A power-angle-based adaptive overcurrent protection scheme for grid-forming inverter under large grid disturbances," *IEEE Trans. Industrial Electronics*, vol. 70, no. 6, pp. 5927–5936, June 2023.
- [16] T. Zheng, et al., "Flexible unbalanced control with peak current limitation for virtual synchronous generator under voltage sags," *Journal of Modern Pow. Systems and Clean Energy*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 61–72, 2018.
- [17] A. Mihai Gross, et al., "Energy management in converter-interfaced renewable energy sources through ultracapacitors for provision of ancillary services", *Sustain. Energy, Grids and Networks*, vol. 32, 2022.
- [18] B. Craciun, et al., "Frequency support functions in large PV power plants with active power reserves," *IEEE JESTPE*, vol. 2(4), pp. 849–858, 2014.
- [19] L. Hadjidemetriou, et al., "A Robust synchronization to enhance the power quality of renewable energy systems," *IEEE Trans. Industrial Electronics*, vol. 62, no. 8, pp. 4858–4868, 2015.
- [20] X. Wang, Y. W. Li, F. Blaabjerg, and P. C. Loh, "Virtual-impedance-based control for voltage-source and current-source converters," *IEEE Trans. Power Electronics*, vol. 30, no. 12, pp. 7019–7037, 2015.